

MATHEMATICAL SCIENCES

OPTIMAL SELECTION FOR REPAIRMENT OF NON-OPERATING OIL WELLS WITH DATA INTERVALS IN OIL AND GAS PRODUCTION DEPARTMENTS

K. Mammadov,

Baku State University
Baku city, Zahid Khalilov, 23

Azerbaijan

Institute of Control Systems

Azerbaijan

Baku city, Bakhtiyar Vahabzadeh street, 68

A. Mammadova,

Institute of Control Systems

Azerbaijan

Baku city, Bakhtiyar Vahabzadeh street, 68

I. Bakhshaliyeva,

Institute of Control Systems

Azerbaijan

Baku city, Bakhtiyar Vahabzadeh street, 68

H. Valiyev

Azerbaijan Technical University

Azerbaijan

Baku city, Hussein Javid prospect, 25

Abstract

The issue of optimal selection for the operation of non-operating oil wells in any oil production department with the initial data which are in the form of intervals is viewed in this article. A mathematical model of this problem is established and algorithms are worked out for finding its suboptimistic and subpessimistic solutions.

Keywords: Interval knapsack issue, special restrictions, optimistic and pessimistic issue, optimistic and pessimistic solutions.

Introduction.

Suppose that a certain number of oil and gas wells under any oil production department do not operate. This can be because of various reasons. It is clear, that if we eliminate these reasons, in other words, if we repair these wells, they will work and give a certain income.

Suppose, that n number of wells need to be repaired in any oil production department. Assume that, the repair of well number j ($j = \overline{1, n}$) requires a_j ($j = \overline{1, n}$) expense and if this well works, c_j ($j = \overline{1, n}$) amount of income (profit, profit, etc.) to be obtained. Suppose, that the department has allocated fund of a total b

quantity for repairment. In addition, taking into account the social situation (for example, the maintenance of being employed of employees working with inoperative wells, etc.), the management at least have to provide running of r number of wells.

Under these conditions, we must select such wells for repairing, so that the total expenses for them does not exceed the amount of allocated b , at least r number of wells are repaired, and this time obtained income is to be maximum. In order to write a mathematical model of this problem, let us accept the unknowns x_j ($j = \overline{1, n}$) as follows.

$$x_j = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if well number } j \text{ is repaired,} \\ 0, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

The mathematical model of the problem we are considering within these notations is as follows:

$$\sum_{j=1}^n c_j x_j \rightarrow \max, \quad (1)$$

$$\sum_{j=1}^n a_j x_j \leq b, \quad (2)$$

$$\sum_{j=1}^n x_j \geq r, \quad (3)$$

$$x_j = 0 \vee 1, (j = \overline{1, n}). \quad (4)$$

Here c_j , a_j ($j = \overline{1, n}$), b and r are positive constants. We can take them as integers without breaking the generality.

Note that (1), (2), and (4) is a known knapsack problem, and certain methods have been developed to find its exact or approximate (suboptimal) solutions [5, 7, 12, 14] and so on. Recall that problems (1), (2) and (4) are NP-complete, which means belong to the class of difficult solved problems. Therefore, the problem (1)-(4) will also be from the same class. However, only condition (3) distinguishes (1)-(4) from the known knapsack problem.

It should be noted that, issues of type (1)-(4) have been viewed in [5, 11, 12, etc.]. It is important to take another real situation into account. Thus, when c_j ($j = \overline{1, n}$) incomes, a_j ($j = \overline{1, n}$) expenses and the allocated

b –funds in the case of (1)-(4) are given as constant numbers, may not describe the reviewed process adequately (equivalently). This is because, during a certain plan period a_j ($j = \overline{1, n}$.) expense, c_j ($j = \overline{1, n}$) income and allocated b fund that are spent for j number of well might not be given in a concrete quantity. Therefore, in a modern market economy, we obtain a more realistic mathematical model by allowing these numbers to change within certain intervals. Such a model is written in the next paragraph and is to be developed a certain solution.

Main part.

Let's look at the issue as follows.

$$\sum_{j=1}^n [c_j, \bar{c}_j] x_j \rightarrow \max, \quad (5)$$

$$\sum_{j=1}^n [a_j, \bar{a}_j] x_j \leq [b, \bar{b}], \quad (6)$$

$$\sum_{j=1}^n x_j \geq r, \quad (7)$$

$$x_j = 0 \vee 1 \quad (j = \overline{1, n}). \quad (8)$$

Here $1 \leq \underline{c}_j \leq \bar{c}_j$, $1 \leq \underline{a}_j \leq \bar{a}_j \leq \underline{c}_j$, ($j = \overline{1, n}$), $1 \leq \underline{b} < \bar{b}$ and r are given integers.

On the other hand, while well number j ($j = \overline{1, n}$) is being operated, the maximum expense of repairing of this should not exceed the minimum income provided by this well number j ($j = \overline{1, n}$). Therefore, the natural condition $1 \leq \underline{a}_j \leq \bar{a}_j \leq \underline{c}_j$ ($j = \overline{1, n}$) must be satisfied.

A possible solution of this problem is considered as a n -dimensional vector $X = (x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n)$ that satisfies the conditions (6)-(8). The optimal solution of this problem is assumed one of the possible solutions, so because of it the function (5) receives the maximum value. Note that, in order to satisfy condition (6), the intervals of several different sizes must not be greater than the total given interval. On the other hand, the maximum value of the function (5) means that the sum of certain different size intervals must be the maximum. However, the fulfillment of such conditions is not single-valued determined mathematically or economically. Therefore, this type of problem had being studied by different authors and have been proposed solutions with different meanings [1- 4, 6, 8-11, 13, etc.].

In all these works, a representative is selected for each interval according to the certain rules and constructed a corresponding classical problem. The solution of the problem is based on certain strategies. We believe that the optimistic and pessimistic strategies chosen in [10] are more realistic for interval issues, by both mathematically and economically. Therefore, on the basis of the problem (5)-(8) we construct the following two optimistic and pessimistic issues.

Optimistic issue:

$$\sum_{j=1}^n \bar{c}_j x_j \rightarrow \max, \quad (9)$$

$$\sum_{j=1}^n \underline{a}_j x_j \leq \bar{b}, \quad (10)$$

$$\sum_{j=1}^n x_j \geq r, \quad (11)$$

$$x_j = 0 \vee 1, \quad (j = \overline{1, n}). \quad (12)$$

Pessimistic issue:

$$\sum_{j=1}^n \underline{c}_j x_j \rightarrow \max, \quad (13)$$

$$\sum_{j=1}^n \bar{a}_j x_j \leq \underline{b}, \quad (14)$$

$$\sum_{j=1}^n x_j \geq r, \quad (15)$$

$$x_j = 0 \vee 1 \quad (j = \overline{1, n}). \quad (16)$$

Note that both (9)-(12) and (13)-(16) are Bull programming problems with special restricted conditions.

Methodology.

We will research the (9)-(12) optimistic problem and work out an algorithm to solve it. However, the existence of a solution of this problem depends on the number r in condition (11).

Obviously, if $r > n$, the range of possible solutions of the problem (9)-(12) is an empty set. If $r = 0$, then (11) does not create a conditional restriction. Therefore, the maximum possible value of r must be found for the presence of a solution of the problem (9)-(12).

For this purpose, let us prove the following theorem:

Theorem: Without breaking the generality, assume that the coefficients \underline{a}_j ($j = \overline{1, n}$) in the condition (10) are arranged in a non-decreasing direction. Which means

$$a_1 \leq a_2 \leq \dots \leq a_n.$$

Then, the necessary and sufficient condition for the existence of the solution of the problem (9)-(12) is the satisfaction of the condition $r \leq p$. Here p is found by the condition

$$\sum_{j=1}^p \underline{a}_j \leq \bar{b} \text{ and } \sum_{j=1}^{p+1} \underline{a}_j > \bar{b} \quad (17)$$

Proof. Necessity. Suppose that there is a solution of the problem (9)-(12). Then that solution must satisfy the inequality (10). Condition (17) indicates that the number of units in any solution of a problem cannot exceed p . Therefore, the condition $r \leq p$ must be met for the maximum number of wells r to be repaired.

Sufficiency. Suppose that, condition $r \leq p$ is paid. Showing that there is a solution to (9)-(12). Condition (17) provides directly that in any solution of the problem (9)-(12) there can be a maximum of 1 p . Then there is a solution to the problem (9)-(12) since the condition $r \leq p$ is satisfied.

Now let's work out a method that finds the optimal solution to the problem (9)-(12). To do this, we need to write an algorithm that finds possible solutions of inequality (10) that holds at least r units. Obviously, when using such an algorithm, it is necessary to find solutions that hold $r, r + 1, \dots, p$ units.

Therefore, we write an algorithm for finding possible solutions of inequality (10) that holds k units.

Algorithm

Step 0: Suppose that the numbers $n, k, r, a_1 \leq a_2 \leq \dots \leq a_n$ are given. In the beginning we accept $k = r$.

Step 1: We accept $v := n; z_i := i, i = 1, 2, \dots, k - 1$, and

$$S := \sum_{i=1}^{k-1} a_{z_i}$$

Step 2: We check that $S + a_v > b$. If "yes", go to step 3, if "not", go to step 4.

Step 3: We accept $v := v - 1$. Let's check $v > z_{k-1}$. If "yes", go to step 2, if "not", go to step 10.

Step 4: We accept $y_{z_i} := 1, i = 1, 2, \dots, k - 1$ and $y_j = 1$ in turn for $j = z_{k-1} + 1, z_{k-1} + 2, \dots, v$, we make the other y_j equal to zero. We obtain a total of $v - z_{k-1}$ possible solutions.

Step 5: We accept $j := 0$.

Step 6: We accept $j := j + 1$ and check $j > k - 1$. If "yes", go to step 10, if "not", go to step 7.

Step 7: We check $z_{k-j} < v - j$. If "yes", then $S := S - p_{z_{k-j}} + p_{z_{k-j+1}}, z_{k-j} := z_{k-j} + 1$. Go to step 8. If "no", go to step 6.

Step 8: $S := S - p_{z_i} + p_{z_{i-1}+1}, z_i := z_{i-1} + 1$ for each $i := k - j + 1, k - j + 2, \dots, k - 1$.

Step 9: We accept $v := n$. Go to step 2.

Step 10: Stop

Note that in the development of this algorithm we used an analogue algorithm is given in [15].

Thus, we perform the following operations to find the optimal solution of the problem (9) -(12).

First, by writing $k = r$ in the algorithm, we find all possible solutions of the inequality (10) that holds r units. Among these solutions, we calculate and remember the one that gives the greatest value to the function (9). Suppose that this value is $f(r)$ and the solution that gives this value is $X^r = (x_1^r, x_2^r, \dots, x_n^r)$.

Then, by accepting $k = r + 1$, let's again find all possible solutions of the inequality (10) by the same algorithm, denote by $f(r + 1)$ the largest of the values of the function (10) corresponding to these solutions, and the solution giving this value is to be $X^{r+1} = (x_1^{r+1}, x_2^{r+1}, \dots, x_n^{r+1})$.

It is obvious that, $f(r^*)$ is the maximum value of the numerical function (9) found from the relation

$$\max \{ f(r), f(r + 1), \dots, f(p) \} = f(r^*)$$

and the solution $X^* = (x_1^*, x_2^*, \dots, x_n^*)$ is the optimal solution of the problem (9)-(12) corresponding to that value $f(r^*)$.

Note that since the problem (9)-(12) is called an optimistic problem, the X^* optimal solution of this

problem will be the optimistic solution of the problem (5)-(7).

Finally, the optimal solution of the pessimistic problem (13)-(16) can be found exactly by the same way as the process above. This solution will be a pessimistic solution to the problem (5)-(7).

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